

Willingness to Get a COVID-19 Vaccine and Its Associated Factors Among Bus Drivers in a Large City in Ethiopia: An Institution Based Cross-Sectional Study

Eden Efreem Mersiehazen (MD)¹, Hanna Feleke Gebremicheal (MPH)², Ayantu Tesfaye Lemma (MD, MPH)³

¹Woldia University, Woldia, North Wollo, Amhara region, Ethiopia

²School of Public Health, St. Paul's Hospital Millennium Medical College, Addis Ababa, Ethiopia

³Department of Internal Medicine, St. Paul's Hospital Millennium Medical College, Addis, Ababa, Ethiopia

*Correspondence: efremeden@gmail.com

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ABSTRACT

Background: As the Coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) pandemic continues to pose a global threat, the most effective strategy is to implement preventive measures, including vaccination. This is especially true for high-risk groups, such as transportation workers, who constantly engage with a number of people. Vaccination plays an even greater role in resource-constrained settings with strained healthcare infrastructure by curbing disease transmission and severity. Despite its importance, vaccination hesitancy, driven by various factors, remains a serious global concern. To safely attain herd immunity, investigating factors that influence vaccine acceptance can help design interventions to enhance acceptability and uptake. Therefore, the aim of this study was to determine the willingness to get a COVID-19 vaccination and to identify associated factors among bus drivers in a large city in Ethiopia.

Methods: An analytic cross-sectional study was conducted from August 16 to October 10 2021, among 184 randomly selected bus drivers working at Shegole bus station, one of the largest depots in Ethiopia's capital, Addis Ababa. Data was summarized using frequency and percentages. Binary logistic regression analysis was run at 5% level of significance to identify significant factors associated with willingness to get a COVID-19 vaccination. Results were interpreted using adjusted odds ratio (AOR) with 95% CI.

Results: The willingness to get COVID-19 vaccination was 34.8%. The perception of being at a higher risk of becoming infected (AOR=3.09, 95% CI=1.38-6.92, p=0.006) and the perception of being susceptible to severe infection and death (AOR=3.17, 95% CI=1.46-6.88, P=0.003) were significantly associated factors.

Conclusions: The level of willingness to get vaccinated was very low and inadequate to achieve herd immunity. Healthcare planners should design interventions that address risk perception with clear information, counter misinformation through trusted voices, promote convenient vaccination at bus depots, and emphasize the social good of protecting communities through driver vaccination.

Key words: COVID-19 Vaccine, Bus drivers, Cross-sectional study, Binary logistic regression, Ethiopia.

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